

STUDIES IN SULPHANILAMIDES. PART VIII. *p*-ACETSULPHANILAMIDE
DERIVATIVES SUBSTITUTED IN N¹-POSITION BY MONO- AND
DI-SUBSTITUTED THIURETS

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The preparation and chemical properties of thirteen new N¹-substituted sulphanilamide derivatives of mono- and di-substituted thiurets are described along with those of the derivative obtained from xanthane hydride. The acetsulphanilamide compounds get completely decomposed on hydrolysis.

The well reputed sulphanilamide drugs namely, Sulphapyridine (I), Sulphadiazine (II), Sulphathiazole (III) and Sulphaguanidine (IV) possess the structural factor N-C=N in common, the carbon atom (marked with an asterisk) being connected with another carbon or nitrogen or sulphur. The present work was undertaken with a view to finding out the bactericidal properties of compounds possessing this important grouping (N-C=N) and containing at the same time two atoms of sulphur in the hetero rings. Sulphanilamide compounds of mono- and di-substituted thiurets (V, VI) satisfy the above two factors, and in this part is given an account of the preparation of several compounds of this series, as also that derived from xanthane hydride (VII).

The structure of the *p*-acetsulphanil derivatives of thiurets immediately follows from that of thiurets. The derivatives of disubstituted thiurets can only have structure (V), whereas those of monosubstituted thiurets may have either (VI) or (VIII).

With alkali the acetsulphanilyl derivative of phenylthiuret decomposes into sulphur and the salts of phenyliminocyanaminothiocarbonic acid, sulphanilic acid and acetic acid. This behaviour is similar to that of acetyl-xanthane hydride (IX) which with alkali decomposes into sulphur, and salts of cyanaminothiocarbonic acid and acetic acid (*Annalen*, 1904, 331, 276) and hence the acetsulphanilyl derivatives have a similar structure, namely (VI).

The aryl and aryl-alkyl thiurets have been prepared by treating primary amines or secondary amines with xanthane hydride whereby mono- ω -nitrogen substituted dithiobiurets are formed, which in turn are oxidised by iodine or ferric chloride to the corresponding monosubstituted or disubstituted thiuret hydrihalides (*Annalen*, 1893, 275, 43; Bayer & Co., D.R.P., 68,697; *Annalen*, 1906, 347, 171; 1912, 394, 265; 1908, 361, 304; 1907, 356, 184; *Ber.*, 1884, 17, 584; 1895, 28, 1099). Attempts to extend the same method to the preparation of alkyl thiurets did not succeed. The latter have been best prepared from mustard oils which react with sodium cyanamide to give sodium salts of N-alkyl-N'-cyanothiureas, which in turn are readily converted into the corresponding alkyl dithiobiurets on treatment with hydrogen sulphide (*Ber.*, 1892, 25, 753; 1886, 19, 449; 1890, 23, 1663). The latter could be oxidised as in the previous method by iodine or ferric chloride to give the thiuret hydrihalides.

The acetsulphanilyl derivatives have been prepared by condensing *p*-acetsulphanilyl chloride with the thiuret hydrihalides (mostly hydriodides and sometimes hydrochlorides) in acetone solution in presence of pyridine. *p*-Acetsulphanilyl chloride is prepared from acetanilide by reaction with chlorosulphonic acid. The acetsulphanilyl derivatives are isolated by diluting the reaction mixture after 12 hours with enough water when the derivatives separate out and are purified by crystallisation from alcohol.

The hydrolysis of the acetsulphanilyl compounds to the free bases could not be carried out under any conditions. Both acid and alkaline hydrolysis seem to disrupt the entire molecule with the separation of sulphur and sulphanilic acid.

Attempts have been made to condense *p*-acetsulphanilyl chloride with the oxidation product of thiourea, namely bis (aminoiminomethyl) disulphide in the form of its dihydrochloride. It will be seen that this compound has a close resemblance to thiurets. The condensation was sought to be effected in acetone medium in presence of pyridine; but no product could be isolated by the usual method. Attempts to condense *S*-carbethoxyisothiourea hydrochloride and isothiourea-*S*-formamidine under similar conditions also failed.

EXPERIMENTAL

Xanthane hydride was prepared by Chattaway and Stevens' method (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1897, 71, 607).

*N*¹-(*p*-Acetsulphanilyl)-phenylthiuret.—In a 250 c.c. flask was placed phenylthiuret hydriodide (23 g.), acetone (150 c.c.) and pyridine (35 c.c.). The resulting homogeneous solution was cooled to 15-20° and well powdered *p*-acetsulphanilyl chloride (17 g.) gradually added while keeping the solution well stirred. The solution turned red as reaction started and deepened in colour with its progress. The addition took about 15 minutes. The reaction mixture was taken out of the cooling bath and allowed to stand at room temperature for 12 hours, after which it was poured into water (1 litre). The crude resin-

like product, which was precipitated, was separated by decantation, agitated with a small amount of alcohol to remove the red colour and filtered. A single crystallisation from alcohol gave the pure product, m.p. 174°, yield 12 g. (Found : C, 47.65 ; H, 3.68 ; N, 13.71 ; S, 23.85. $C_{16}H_{14}O_3N_4S_3$ requires C, 47.3 ; H, 3.45 ; N, 13.79 ; S, 23.64 per cent).

N^1 -(*p*-Acetsulphanilyl)-*p*-tolylthiuret.—*p*-Tolylthiuret hydriodide (12 g.) was placed along with acetone (80 c.c.) and pyridine (20 c.c.) in a conical flask and the resulting clear solution cooled to 15-20°. Acetsulphanilyl chloride (8 g.) was added over a period of 15 minutes, keeping the solution well stirred. The reaction mixture was then allowed to stand overnight after which it was poured into water (600 c.c.) and the product purified as before, m.p. 167°, yield 6 g. (Found : N, 13.23 ; S, 22.5. $C_{17}H_{16}O_3N_4S_3$ requires N, 13.34 ; S, 22.87 per cent).

N^1 -(*p*-Acetsulphanilyl)-*o*-tolylthiuret was prepared by interacting *o*-tolylthiuret hydriodide (5 g.) with *p*-acetsulphanilyl chloride (3.5 g.) in the presence of acetone (35 c.c.) and pyridine (10 c.c.). It was purified by crystallisation from alcohol, m.p. 164°, yield 2 g. (Found : N, 13.17 ; S, 22.67. $C_{17}H_{16}O_3N_4S_3$ requires N, 13.34 ; S, 22.87 per cent).

N^1 -(*p*-Acetsulphanilyl)-*o*-methoxyphenylthiuret was obtained by interacting *o*-methoxyphenylthiuret hydriodide (12.6 g.) with acetsulphanilyl chloride (8 g.) in acetone medium (80 c.c.) in presence of pyridine (20 c.c.). Isolation and purification as before, m.p. 153°; yield 6 g. (Found : N, 12.44 ; S, 21.83. $C_{17}H_{16}O_4N_4S_2$ requires N, 12.84 ; S, 22.02 per cent).

o-Methoxyphenylthiuret hydriodide was obtained by the oxidation of an alcoholic solution of *o*-methoxyphenyldithiobiuret with iodine. Crystallisation from alcohol as in the corresponding cases, m.p. 199-200°, yield quantitative. (Found : N, 11.31 ; S, 17.65. $C_9H_{10}ON_3IS_2$ requires N, 11.44 ; S, 17.44 per cent).

N^1 -(*p*-Acetsulphanilyl)-*p*-methoxyphenylthiuret was prepared by condensing *p*-methoxyphenylthiuret hydriodide (6 g.) with *p*-acetsulphanilyl chloride (4 g.) in the presence of acetone (40 c.c.) and pyridine (10 c.c.). Isolation and purification by the usual method, m.p. 160-61°, yield 3 g. (Found : N, 12.51 ; S, 21.77. $C_{17}H_{16}O_4N_4S_2$ requires N, 12.84 ; S, 22.02 per cent).

p-Methoxyphenyldithiobiuret was obtained by condensing *p*-anisidine (10 g.) with xanthane hydride (10 g.) by heating on a water-bath for half an hour. The amine was removed by boiling with 50% alcohol (150 c.c.), the alcoholic solution chilled and the resulting crystals freed from sulphur by dissolving in 10% sodium hydroxide solution (80 c.c.), filtering the solution and acidifying the filtrate. It crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 165°, yield 10 to 12 g. (Found : N, 17.35 ; S, 26.6. $C_9H_{11}ON_3S_2$ requires N, 17.43 ; S, 26.56 per cent).

p-Methoxyphenylthiuret Hydriodide.—Oxidation of a saturated alcoholic solution of the dithiobiuret with iodine yielded the hydriodide which was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 182°, yield quantitative. (Found : N, 11.52 ; S, 17.27. $C_9H_{10}ON_3IS_2$ requires N, 11.44 ; S, 17.44 per cent).

N^1 -(*p*-Acetsulphanilyl)-*p*-ethoxyphenylthiuret was prepared from the corresponding thiuret hydriodide (4.1 g.) and acetsulphanilyl chloride (2.6 g.) as before, m.p. 183°, yield 2 g. (Found : N, 12.4 ; S, 21.18. $C_{18}H_{18}O_4N_4S_2$ requires N, 12.45 ; S, 21.33 per cent).

p-Ethoxyphenylthiuret hydriodide was obtained by oxidation of an alcoholic solution of the dithiobiuret by iodine, followed by recrystallisation from alcohol, m.p. 194°, yield quantitative. (Found : N, 10.96 ; S, 16.74. $C_{10}H_{12}ON_3IS_2$ requires N, 11.03 ; S, 16.8 per cent).

N^1 -(*p*-Acetsulphanilyl)-*o*-ethoxyphenylthiuret.—*o*-Ethoxyphenylthiuret hydrochloride (6 g.) was reacted with acetsulphanilyl chloride (4.7 g.) in acetone solution (50 c.c.) in presence of pyridine (10 c.c.). Final purification was done by crystallisation from alcohol, m.p. 189°, yield 3.5 g. (Found : N, 12.54 ; S, 21.46. $C_{16}H_{18}O_2N_4S_2$ requires N, 12.45 ; S, 21.33 per cent).

N^1 -(*p*-Acetsulphanilyl)- α -naphthylthiuret was obtained from the corresponding thiuret hydriodide (5.5 g.) and acetsulphanilyl chloride (3.6 g.), m.p. above 300°, yield 1.4 g. (Found : N, 12.43 ; S, 21.2. $C_{20}H_{16}O_2N_4S_2$ requires N, 12.28 ; S, 21.05 per cent).

α -Naphthylthiuret.— α -Naphthylamine (15 g.) and xanthane hydride (10 g.) were heated together on a boiling water-bath for 20-25 minutes. The excess of amine was removed as before by boiling with 50% alcohol (120 c.c.) and the purification done by dissolving in 10% alkali (80 c.c.) and reprecipitating with acid. The product was finally purified by crystallisation from acetic acid or alcohol, m.p. 246°, yield 9 g. (Found : N, 16.23 ; S, 24.4. $C_{12}H_{11}N_2S_2$ requires N, 16.09 ; S, 24.52 per cent).

α -Naphthylthiuret hydriodide was prepared by the usual method, m.p. 237°, yield quantitative. (Found : N, 10.77 ; S, 16.7. $C_{12}H_{10}N_3IS_2$ requires N, 10.85 ; S, 16.54 per cent).

N^1 -(*p*-Acetsulphanilyl) β -naphthylthiuret.— β -Naphthylthiuret hydrochloride (3 g.) and acetsulphanilyl chloride (2.4 g.) were condensed together in acetone solution (30 c.c.) in presence of pyridine (5 c.c.). The acetone solution unlike in previous experiments was kept refluxing initially for an hour, and subsequently worked up as before, m.p. 217-218°, yield 2.4 g. (Found : N, 12.07 ; S, 20.86. $C_{20}H_{16}O_2N_4S_2$ requires N, 12.28 ; S, 21.05 per cent).

N^1 -(*p*-Acetsulphanilyl)-phenylmethylthiuret was prepared as usual from acetsulphanilyl chloride (4 g.) and phenylmethylthiuret hydriodide (6 g.). Initial refluxing for an hour was found to be necessary. The product was finally crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 191°, yield 2.3 g. (Found : N, 13.18 ; S, 22.93. $C_{17}H_{16}O_2N_4S_2$ requires N, 13.34 ; S, 22.87 per cent).

N^1 -(*p*-Acetsulphanilyl)-phenylethylthiuret was prepared by the usual method. Initial refluxing of the acetone solution was helpful, m.p. 183°, yield 41% of theory. (Found : N, 12.81 ; S, 22.04. $C_{18}H_{18}O_2N_4S_2$ requires N, 12.9 ; S, 22.112 per cent).

Phenylethylthiuret hydriodide was prepared and purified by the general method, m.p. 196°, yield quantitative. (Found : N, 11.39 ; S, 17.65. $C_{10}H_{12}N_3IS_2$ requires N, 11.5 ; S, 17.54 per cent).

p-Acetsulphanilyl Derivatives of Monoalkylthiurets.—Attempts to extend the method used for the preparation of arylthiurets to alkyl dithiobiurets failed. Experiments were conducted in which xanthane hydride, dissolved in pyridine solution, was sought to be condensed with methylamine, which was bubbled through the solution, the latter being heated subsequently in an autoclave for periods of time varying from half an hour

to two hours. But nothing separated except sulphur on diluting the reaction mixture with water and adding acid. Some experiments were conducted by heating on a water-bath sealed tubes containing liquified methylamine and xanthane hydride. The corresponding dithiobiuret did not seem to be formed. Therefore the method described by Hecht was used for the preparation of alkyl dithiobiurets and therefrom the thiuret hydriodides. Methyl and allyl dithiobiurets were obtained in 50 and 27.5% yields respectively

*N*¹-(*p*-Acetsulphanilyl) methylthiuret was obtained by condensing a solution of the thiuret hydriodide (5.6 g.) in a mixture of acetone (35 c.c.) and pyridine (5 c.c.) with acet-sulphanilyl chloride (4.8 g.). Initial refluxing for an hour was necessary, m.p. 148°, yield 2.2 g. (Found : N, 16.32 ; S, 27.68. $C_{11}H_{12}O_2N_2S_2$ requires N, 16.28 ; S, 27.9 per cent).

Methylthiuret Hydriodide.—The procedure adopted for the preparation of aromatic thiuret hydriodides was used without any modification, m.p. 131°, yield almost quantitative. (Found : N, 15.41 ; S, 23.09. $C_9H_8N_2S_2$ requires N, 15.27 ; S, 23.28 per cent).

*N*¹-(*p*-Acetsulphanilyl)allylthiuret.—Acetsulphanilyl chloride (2.4 g.) was condensed with allylthiuret hydriodide (3 g.) in acetone medium (25 c.c.) in presence of pyridine (4 c.c.). The condensation product was isolated and purified as before, m.p. 165°, yield 1.3 g. (Found : N, 15.22 ; S, 25.84. $C_{13}H_{14}O_2N_2S_2$ requires N, 15.14 ; S, 25.95 per cent).

Allylthiuret Hydriodide.—The usual procedure of oxidation in alcoholic solution was adopted, m.p. 110-12°, yield quantitative. (Found : N, 14.06 ; S, 21.47. $C_5H_8N_2S_2$ requires N, 13.95 ; S, 21.26 per cent).

Condensation of p-Acetsulphanilyl Chloride with Xanthane Hydride.—Xanthane hydride (3 g.) was reacted with *p*-acetsulphanilyl chloride (5 g.) in acetone (25 c.c.) in presence of pyridine (5 c.c.). The solution which turned red was left overnight and then poured into water (250 c.c.). The substance was separated by decantation of the liquid and purified by crystallisation from alcohol after treatment with norit, whereby brown crystals were obtained, m.p. 197°, yield 2.8 g. (Found : N, 11.92 ; S, 37.04. $C_{10}H_8O_2N_2S_4$ requires N, 12.11 ; S, 36.89 per cent).

Action of Alkali on N (*p*-acetsulphanilyl) *phenylthiuret*.—*N*¹-(*p*-Acetsulphanilyl)phenylthiuret (2 g.) was treated with an aqueous solution (10 c.c.) of potassium hydroxide (0.5 g.). In about 30 minutes, the compound was completely decomposed. The solution was filtered and the filtrate was found to answer all the reactions characteristic of salts of sulphanilic acid and cyanaminophenylthiocarbamic acid (*Ber.*, 1886, 19, 449). Sulphanilic acid was precipitated on acidifying the solution.